

On the K -power free number sequence

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is to study the distribution properties of the k -power free numbers, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords k -power free number, mean value, asymptotic formula

§1. Introduction

A natural number n is called a k -power free number if it can not be divided by any p^k , where p is a prime. One can obtain all k -power free number by the following method: From the set of natural numbers (except 0 and 1).

–take off all multiples of 2^k , (i.e $2^k, 2^{k+1}, 2^{k+2} \dots$).

–take off all multiples of 3^k .

–take off all multiples of 5^k .

... and so on (take off all multiples of all k -power primes).

When $k = 3$, the k -power free number sequence is 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, ... In reference [1], Professor F. Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the k -power free number sequence. About this problem, Zhang Tianping had given an asymptotic formula in reference [3]. That is, he proved that

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} \omega^2(n) = \frac{x(\ln \ln x)^2}{\zeta(k)} + O(x(\ln \ln x)),$$

where $\omega(n)$ denotes the number of prime divisors of n , $\zeta(k)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

This paper as a note of [3], we use the analytic method to obtain a more accurate asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. Let k be a positive integer with $k \geq 2$, B denotes the set of all k -power free number. Then we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} \omega^2(n) = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \left(x(\ln \ln x)^2 + C_1 x \ln \ln x + C_2 x \right) + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right),$$

where $\zeta(k)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, C_1 and C_2 are both constants.

§2. Some Lemmas

To complete the proof of the theorem, we need following several Lemmas.

Lemma 1. For any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega(n) = x \ln \ln x + Ax + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln x}\right),$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \omega^2(n) = x(\ln \ln x)^2 + ax \ln \ln x + bx + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right),$$

where $A = \gamma + \sum_p \left(\ln\left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) + \frac{1}{p}\right)$, a and b are two computable constants.

Proof. See reference [2].

Lemma 2. Let $\mu(n)$ be the Möbius function, then for any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the following identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu(n)\omega(n)}{n^s} = -\frac{1}{\zeta(s)} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^s - 1}.$$

Proof. See reference [3].

Lemma 3. Let $k \geq 2$ be a fixed integer, then for any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(m)\mu(d) = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \left(x(\ln \ln x)^2 + ax \ln \ln x + bx\right) + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right).$$

Proof. From Lemma 1 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(m)\mu(d) &= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{m \leq \frac{x}{d^k}} \omega^2(m) \\ &= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{x}{d^k} (\ln \ln \frac{x}{d^k})^2 + a \frac{x}{d^k} \ln \ln \frac{x}{d^k} + b \frac{x}{d^k} + O\left(\frac{\frac{x}{d^k} \ln \ln \frac{x}{d^k}}{\ln \frac{x}{d^k}}\right) \right) \\ &= x \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \left(\ln \ln x + \ln\left(1 - \frac{k \ln d}{\ln x}\right) \right)^2 + ax \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \ln \ln \frac{x}{d^k} \\ &\quad + bx \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The first term on the right hand side of (1) is

$$\begin{aligned} &x \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \left(\ln \ln x + \ln\left(1 - \frac{k \ln d}{\ln x}\right) \right)^2 \\ &= x(\ln \ln x)^2 \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} + O\left(x \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{|\mu(d)|}{d^k} \cdot \frac{k \ln d}{\ln x} \cdot \ln \ln x\right) + O\left(x \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{|\mu(d)|}{d^k} \cdot \frac{\ln^2 d}{\ln^2 x}\right) \\ &= \frac{x(\ln \ln x)^2}{\zeta(k)} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} (\ln \ln x)^2\right) + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right) + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right) \\ &= \frac{x(\ln \ln x)^2}{\zeta(k)} + O\left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x}\right). \end{aligned}$$

The second term on the right hand side of (1) is

$$\begin{aligned} ax \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \ln \ln \frac{x}{d^k} &= ax \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \ln \ln x + ax \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} \ln \left(1 - \frac{k \ln d}{\ln x} \right) \\ &= \frac{ax \ln \ln x}{\zeta(k)} + O \left(x \sum_{d > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{|\mu(d)|}{d^k} \ln \ln x \right) + O \left(x \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{|\mu(d)|}{d^k} \frac{\ln d}{\ln x} \right) \\ &= \frac{ax \ln \ln x}{\zeta(k)} + O \left(\frac{x}{\ln x} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The third term on the right hand side of (1) is

$$bx \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} = bx \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu(d)}{d^k} + O \left(bx \sum_{d > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{1}{d^k} \right) = \frac{bx}{\zeta(k)} + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right).$$

From the calculations above we get the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(n) \mu(d) = \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \left(x (\ln \ln x)^2 + ax \ln \ln x + bx \right) + O \left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right).$$

This proves Lemma 3.

Lemma 4. Let any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(d) \mu(d) = A_1 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} (\ln \ln x)^2 \right),$$

where $A_1 = \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{\omega^2(d) \mu(d)}{d^k}$ is a calculable constant.

Proof. Note that the series $\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(d) \mu(d)$ is convergent, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(d) \mu(d) &= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \omega^2(d) \mu(d) \sum_{m \leq \frac{x}{d^k}} 1 = \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \omega^2(d) \mu(d) \left[\frac{x}{d^k} \right] \\ &= x \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{\omega^2(d) \mu(d)}{d^k} + O \left(x \sum_{d > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{\omega^2(d) |\mu(d)|}{d^k} \right) + O \left(\sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \omega^2(d) |\mu(d)| \right) \\ &= A_1 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} (\ln \ln x)^2 \right) + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} (\ln \ln x^{\frac{1}{k}})^2 \right) \\ &= A_1 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} (\ln \ln x)^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

This proves Lemma 4.

Lemma 5. For any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2((d, m)) \mu(d) = A_2 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \right),$$

where $A_2 = \frac{\mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \frac{\omega^2(u)}{u} \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \frac{\mu(s)}{s}}{d^k}$ is a calculable constant.

Proof. Assume that (u, v) is the greatest common divisor of u and v , then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2((d, m))\mu(d) = \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \sum_{\substack{m \leq \frac{x}{d^k} \\ u|m, (\frac{m}{u}, \frac{d}{u})=1}} \omega^2(u) \\
&= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \sum_{\substack{m \leq \frac{x}{d^k} \\ u|m}} \omega^2(u) \left[\frac{1}{(\frac{m}{u}, \frac{d}{u})} \right] \\
&= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \sum_{\substack{m \leq \frac{x}{d^k} \\ u|m}} \omega^2(u) \sum_{\substack{s|\frac{m}{u} \\ s|\frac{d}{u}}} \mu(s) \\
&= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \sum_{q \leq \frac{x}{d^k s u}} \omega^2(u) \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \mu(s) \\
&= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \omega^2(u) \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \mu(s) \left[\frac{x}{d^k u s} \right] \\
&= \sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \omega^2(u) \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \mu(s) \left(\frac{x}{d^k u s} + O(1) \right) \\
&= x \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{\mu(d) \sum_{u|d} \frac{\omega^2(u)}{u} \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \frac{\mu(s)}{s}}{d^k} + O \left(x \sum_{d > x^{\frac{1}{k}}} \frac{|\mu(d)| \sum_{u|d} \frac{\omega^2(u)}{u} \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} \frac{|\mu(s)|}{s}}{d^k} \right) \\
&\quad + O \left(\sum_{d \leq x^{\frac{1}{k}}} |\mu(d)| \sum_{u|d} \omega^2(u) \sum_{s|\frac{d}{u}} |\mu(s)| \right) \\
&= A_2 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k} + \varepsilon} \right),
\end{aligned}$$

where ε is any positive number. This proves Lemma 5.

Same as the method used in the above Lemmas, we can easily get the following three asymptotic formulas:

Lemma 6. For any real number $x \geq 2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(d)\omega((d, m))\mu(d) = A_3 x + O \left(x^{\frac{1}{k}} \ln \ln x \right), \\
& \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(m)\omega((d, m))\mu(d) = A_4 x \ln \ln x + O \left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right), \\
& \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(d)\omega(m)\mu(d) = C (x \ln \ln x + Ax) + O \left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right),
\end{aligned}$$

where $C = -\frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^k - 1}$, A_3 and A_4 are constants.

§3. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of Theorem. From Lemmas above, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} \omega^2(n) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \omega^2(n) \sum_{d^k | n} \mu(d) = \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(d^k m) \mu(d) \\
 &= \sum_{d^k m \leq x} (\omega(d) + \omega(m) - \omega((d, m)))^2 \mu(d) \\
 &= \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(m) \mu(d) + \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2(d) \mu(d) + \sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega^2((d, m)) \mu(d) \\
 &\quad + 2 \left(\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(d) \omega(m) \mu(d) \right) - 2 \left(\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(d) \omega((d, m)) \mu(d) \right) \\
 &\quad - 2 \left(\sum_{d^k m \leq x} \omega(m) \omega((d, m)) \mu(d) \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} \left(x(\ln \ln x)^2 + C_1 x \ln \ln x + C_2 x \right) + O \left(\frac{x \ln \ln x}{\ln x} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

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